

Connection between high-level ethical principles and tangible system requirements (Morley et al., 2019)

(Adapted from the methodology presented in Chapter II of the “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI” by the European Commission)

*Below each of the 5 principles is a list of requirements (these are related to the ethical issues presented by Prem (2023)).

1. **Beneficence:**

- 1.1. **Stakeholder participation** – to develop systems that are trustworthy and support human prosperity, those affected by the system should be consulted
- 1.2. **Protection of fundamental rights**
- 1.3. **Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI** – the system’s supply chain should be assessed for resource use and energy consumption
- 1.4. **Justification** – the purpose of building the system should be clear and linked to a clear benefit; the system should not be built without a justified reason

2. **Non-Maleficence:**

- 2.1. **Resilience to attacks and security** – AI systems should be protected against vulnerabilities that could allow them to be exploited by adversaries
- 2.2. **Fallback plan and general safety** – AI systems should include safeguards that enable fallback plans in case of issues
- 2.3. **Accuracy** – for example, documentation demonstrating evaluation of whether the system is correctly classifying results
- 2.4. **Privacy and data protection** – AI systems should ensure privacy and data protection throughout the entire system lifecycle
- 2.5. **Reliability and reproducibility** – the system should perform consistently across a variety of scenarios
- 2.6. **Data quality and integrity** – when data is collected, it may contain socially constructed biases, inaccuracies, errors, and mistakes – this must be addressed
- 2.7. **Social impact** – the effects of the system on people’s physical and mental well-being should be carefully considered and monitored

3. **Autonomy:**

- 3.1. **Human agency** – users should be able to make informed, autonomous decisions when interacting with AI systems
- 3.2. **Human oversight** – can be achieved through governance mechanisms such as human-on-the-loop, human-in-the-loop, and human-in-command

4. **Justice:**

- 4.1. **Avoid unfair bias**
- 4.2. **Accessibility and universal design**
- 4.3. **Society and democracy** – the system’s impact on institutions, democracy, and society should be considered broadly
- 4.4. **Auditability** – enabling the evaluation of algorithms, data, and design processes
- 4.5. **Minimization and reporting of negative impacts** – measures should be taken to identify, assess, document, minimize, and respond to potential negative impacts of AI systems

- 4.6. **Trade-offs** – when trade-offs between requirements are necessary, a process should be implemented to explicitly identify and transparently evaluate them
- 4.7. **Redress** – mechanisms should be implemented to respond when things go wrong

5. Explicability:

- 5.1. **Traceability** – the dataset and the process that lead to the system's decisions should be documented
- 5.2. **Explainability** – the ability to explain both the technical processes of an AI system and the related human decisions
- 5.3. **Interpretability**
- 5.4. **Accountability** – Floridi et al., 2018